

ViSketch-GPT: Collaborative Multi-Scale Feature Extraction for Sketch Recognition and Generation*

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the nature of human sketches is challenging because of the wide variation in how they are created. Recognizing complex structural patterns improves both the accuracy in recognizing sketches and the fidelity of the generated sketches. In this work, we introduce **ViSketch-GPT**, a novel algorithm designed to address these challenges through a multi-scale context extraction approach. The model captures intricate details at multiple scales and combines them using an ensemble-like mechanism, where the extracted features work collaboratively to enhance the recognition and generation of key details crucial for classification and generation tasks.

The effectiveness of ViSketch-GPT is validated through extensive experiments on the QuickDraw dataset. Our model *establishes a new benchmark*, significantly **outperforming existing methods** in both classification and generation tasks, with substantial improvements in accuracy and the fidelity of generated sketches.

The proposed algorithm offers a robust framework for understanding complex structures by extracting features that collaborate to recognize intricate details, enhancing the understanding of structures like sketches and making it a versatile tool for various applications in computer vision and machine learning.

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1. Introduction

Recognizing patterns of complex structures is fundamental for both the recognition and generation of visual content. However it becomes particularly challenging in the domain of human sketches where there is no single way to draw, but rather a variety of styles and representations for the same entities. Current approaches struggle to recognize and capture complex patterns, as they often fail to identify the intricate details that distinguish one entity from another, which are essential for accurate recognition and would enable better generation even when treating sketches as vector representations and leveraging NLP techniques to capture intricate temporal and structural dependencies. Vector sketches are inherently represented as ordered sequences of strokes, where each stroke is defined by a series of connected points. This sequential structure aligns naturally with NLP methodologies, which are designed to handle ordered, context-dependent data.

Models like SketchRNN (Ha and Eck (2018)) have demonstrated the importance of leveraging sequential stroke information for sketch generation, employing recurrent architectures (RNNs) to predict the next stroke based on

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previous ones. Building on this, Sketch-BERT (Lin, Fu, Xue and Jiang (2020)) extended the approach by adapting language modeling techniques such as BERT (Devlin, Chang, Lee and Toutanova (2019)) to the sketch domain. This enabled not only sketch generation but also improved recognition and retrieval, capitalizing on the transformer’s ability to capture bidirectional context. By treating sketches as sequences of visual "tokens," these approaches bridge the gap between textual and visual data, unlocking new possibilities for understanding and generating free-hand sketches.

In this work, we present a novel framework that redefines how context is extracted and utilized for both recognition and generation. By decomposing the sketch into smaller patches using the quadtree technique and employing a multi-level context extraction mechanism for each patch, ViSketch-GPT captures contextual information at different scales, allowing each patch to be more accurately characterized. The collaborative integration of these features enables the model to capture intricate details, which are essential for precise recognition and significantly enhance the generation process by maintaining structural coherence.

To evaluate the performance of ViSketch-GPT, we conducted experiments to assess its ability to recognize sketches and the fidelity of the generated sketches. Our results demonstrate that the model **significantly outperforms the state of the art** in classification, surpassing existing methods in both Top-1 and Top-3 accuracy, and demonstrating superior fidelity in sketch generation, as shown by the classifier’s ability to accurately recognize the new generated sketches.

Our contributions are as follows:

1. We introduce a new methodology for capturing intricate details through the collaboration of multi-scale features, enhancing both sketch recognition and generation.
2. We evaluate the methodology through extensive experiments on the QuickDraw dataset, demonstrating its *superior performance compared to state-of-the-art methods* in both sketch recognition and generation.
3. We have optimized our approach to handling *sparse data* through a representation that mitigates potential issues during the generation phase.

2. Related works

Since the introduction of Sketch-a-Net in 2015 (Yu, Yang, Song, Xiang and Hospedales (2015)) as a CNN-based model capable of generating free-hand sketches, significant advancements have been made in this domain in terms of architectures, representations, and datasets. In 2017, Google released QuickDraw, a large-scale sketch dataset comprising over 50 million sketches collected from players worldwide and SketchRNN (Ha and Eck (2018)) was introduced as an RNN-based deep Variational Autoencoder (VAE) capable of generating diverse sketches. Subsequent developments have focused on retrieval methods (Xu, Huang, Yuan, Pang, Song, Xiang, Hospedales, Ma and Guo (2018)), recognition approaches (Xu, Joshi and Bresson (2022); Hu, Li, Song, Xiang and Hospedales (2018)), and abstraction techniques aimed at simplifying sketches while preserving their recognizability (Muhammad, Yang, Song, Xiang and Hospedales (2018)), among others. Additionally, numerous new datasets have emerged, spanning both uni-modal and multi-modal domains, as well as varying levels of granularity (coarse- vs. fine-grained). Uni-modal datasets primarily support tasks such as recognition, retrieval, segmentation, and generation, whereas multi-modal datasets associate sketches with other modalities, including natural images, 3D models, and textual descriptions. Coarse-grained datasets (Eitz, Hays and Alexa (2012); Ha and Eck (2018)) provide more general sketch representations, while fine-grained datasets offer higher levels of detail (Yu, Liu, Song, Xiang, Hospedales and Loy (2016)).

Free-hand sketch tasks can be categorized into *uni-modal* and *multi-modal* tasks based on the type of data involved.

Uni-modal tasks include *recognition*, *retrieval*, *segmentation*, and *generation*. Recognition aims to predict the class of a given sketch (Zhang, Liu, Zhang, Ren, Wang and Cao (2016a); Seddati, Dupont and Mahmoudi (2015); Zhang, Zhang and Qian (2016b); Lin et al. (2020); Guo, Wang, Roman-Rangel, Chao and Rui (2016); Ballester and Araujo (2016); Seddati, Dupont and Mahmoudi (2016); Zhang, She, Liu, Gan, Cao and Foroosh (2019); Jia, Fan, Yu, Liu, Wang and Latecki (2020)). Retrieval focuses on using a query sketch to retrieve similar samples from a dataset or collection (Lin et al. (2020); Wang and Li (2015); Xu et al. (2018); Creswell and Bharath (2016)). This is a particularly challenging task since traditional feature extraction methods (e.g., SIFT (Lowe (2004))) are ineffective due to the difficulty of identifying repeatable feature points across sketches drawn in diverse human styles. Segmentation involves the semantic partitioning of sketches and while conventional segmentation models for natural images could be adapted, the sequential nature of sketches has led to the development of dedicated models tailored to this task (Wu, Qi, Liu and Yang (2018); Qi and Tan (2019); Wang, Lin, Wu, Li, Wang, Luo and He (2019); Kim, Wang, Öztireli and Gross (2018); Kaiyrbekov and Sezgin (2020); Yang, Zhuang, Fu, Wei, Zhou and Zheng (2021); Wang and Li (2024)).

Deep learning-based approaches (Ha and Eck (2018); Cao, Yan, Shi and Chen (2019); Sasaki and Ogata (2018); Li, Gao, Shen, Zhang, Mei and Ren (2020); Ge, Goswami, Zitnick and Parikh (2020); Das, Yang, Hospedales, Xiang and Song (2020); Bhunia, Das, Muhammad, Yang, Hospedales, Xiang, Gryaditskaya and Song (2020); Ribeiro, Bui, Collomosse and Ponti (2020); Das, Yang, Hospedales, Xiang and Song (2021); Tiwari, Biswas and Lladós (2024)) have significantly outperformed traditional sketch generation methods. Sketch generation has numerous practical applications, including synthesizing new sketches, assisting artists in streamlining their design process, and reconstructing corrupted or incomplete sketches.

A pioneering model in this domain is SketchRNN (Ha and Eck (2018)), which remains one of the state-of-the-art approaches for sketch-based abstraction and generalization. SketchRNN is a recurrent neural network-based generative model designed for both conditional and unconditional vector sketch generation. It was trained on QuickDraw, a large-scale dataset of vector drawings collected from "Quick, Draw!", an online game where players were asked to sketch objects from a given category within 20 seconds. The dataset includes hundreds of object categories, each containing 70 training samples, along with 2.5K validation and test samples. The network is formally a Sequence-to-Sequence Variational Autoencoder (VAE), where the encoder is a bidirectional RNN that takes as input the sketch (the sequence defining it) and outputs a latent vector (the concatenation of the two hidden states obtained from the bidirectional RNNs). This latent vector is then transformed via a fully connected layer into a vector representing the mean and standard deviation, which are used to sample a latent vector. This sampled latent vector is provided as input to a decoder (an autoregressive RNN), which samples the subsequent strokes of the sketch.

SketchBERT (Lin et al. (2020)) is a model based on BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers Devlin et al. (2019)) adapted for handling free-hand sketches. It leverages BERT's ability to capture contextual relationships between elements in a sequence to analyze and interpret sketches, treating them as temporal sequences of pen strokes. SketchBERT is designed for sketch recognition and generation tasks, utilizing a pre-trained representation to enhance performance across various computer vision and sketch generation tasks while maintaining high efficiency in the context of unstructured sequential data like sketches.

AI-Sketcher (Cao et al. (2019)) proposes an enhancement of Sketch-RNN for handling multi-class generation, also based on a VAE generative model. They evaluated their method on a single dataset: FaceX. This dataset contains 5 million sketches of male and female facial expressions, and, unlike QuickDraw, the sketches were created by professionals.

VASkeGAN (Balasubramanian, Balasubramanian et al. (2019)) combines a Variational Autoencoder (VAE) with a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) to leverage the strengths of both models. The VAE is used to obtain an efficient representation of the data, while the GAN is employed to generate high-quality images. The goal is to produce visually appealing sketches, benefiting from both the compression capabilities of the VAE and the realistic generation abilities of the GAN. Additionally, a new metric called *SkeScore* was introduced; however, it is only applicable to vector-based generations.

SketchGPT (Tiwari et al. (2024)) employs a sequence-to-sequence autoregressive model for sketch generation and completion by mapping complex sketches into simplified sequences of abstract primitives by leveraging the next token prediction objective strategy to understand sketch patterns, facilitating the creation and completion of drawings and also categorizing them accurately.

3. Methodology

We formulate the problem as follows. We want to train a Neural Network that, given a specific class, is able to generate an image containing a sketch which belongs to the class. More formally, our objective is to learn the conditional distribution $p(S|c)$ so that, given the class label $c \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, it is possible to generate $S \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$, representing a sketch of c . An example of such a task is shown in Figure 1.

We split the generation process into **two stages**: i) pure generation and ii) refinement generation.

In the **pure generation stage**, we tackle the task of modeling the distribution $p(S|c)$ in a much smaller resolution space than the desired one. Specifically, if H, W are the desired dimensions of the sketches, we choose H', W' such that $H' \ll H, W' \ll W$. More formally, this first stage can be defined as the process of inferring the conditional distribution:

$$p(S'|c) \quad \text{where } c \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \text{ and } S' \in \mathbb{R}^{H' \times W'}$$

Figure 1: An example of the task we aim to tackle. Starting from the class label, we aim to generate a sketch belonging to that class.

This simplifies and significantly accelerates the training process on complex shapes like sketches, as working in a lower-dimensional space reduces the complexity of modeling the distribution. Instead of accounting for all highly variable human-specific details, the model can focus on capturing the essential structural characteristics representative of the class, making learning more efficient. To model this distribution, we opted for *diffusion model theory* (Ho, Jain and Abbeel (2020)).

In the **generative refinement** stage, our goal is to *restore the details* that were lost due to the low resolution of S' . For a single S' , there can exist multiple versions of S that contain different details, all statistically plausible.

The objective of the second stage is to learn how to generate a plausible higher resolution version of S' , namely S , by inferring the following conditional distribution:

$$p(S|S', c) \quad \text{where } c \in \mathbb{Z}^+, S \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W} \text{ and } S' \in \mathbb{R}^{H' \times W'}$$

An overview of the two stages is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Overview of the two stages: the first stage operates at a very low resolution to simplify and accelerate modeling; the second stage generates plausible details in a scalable manner.

The way in which this distribution is modeled in the second stage is at the core of the algorithm. Further details are provided in the following sections.

3.1. Spatial Context Extraction for Scalable Refinement

The goal of the **generative refinement** stage is to model the distribution $p(S|S', c)$. In this way, it is possible to plausibly generate a higher resolution version consistent with S' (the output of the previous stage) and with the class c by generatively restoring its details.

A naive approach would be to condition a generative network on S' and c to generate the entire S at its original resolution. Another approach involves dividing S into patches and performing super-resolution on the independent patches. These techniques may fail to fully capture the details we want to restore, let alone generate

patches independently can lead to inconsistencies between adjacent patches previously generated, and generating a large number of patches—especially for sparse data—could be avoided to speed up the generation.

The primary goal is therefore to model the distribution ensuring the coherent reconstruction of missing details while avoiding minimizing redundant generation.

For this reason, we propose a **novel pipeline**.

Given a ground-truth sketch S of the class c , and the low-resolution sketch S' , generated in Stage 1, the training process for the generative refinement performs preliminary steps to allow working effectively at patch level.

The **first step**, performs a trivial *resize* operation on S' , to adapt it to the desired target resolution. We will refer to this resized version as \hat{S} . Then, we build a quadtree by recursively partition \hat{S} only if a certain tile contains significant information or until each leaf reaches the same resolution used in the first stage: $W' \times H'$ (Figure 3). Note that when we build the quadtree, we ensure that *all leaves, regardless of their level, have the same resolution* ($\hat{l}_s \in \mathbb{R}^{W' \times H'}$).

Figure 3: First step of the generative refinement pipeline. Given the output of stage 1, S' is resized to the original resolution \hat{S} and the quadtree is computed.

The **second step**, *copies the quadtree*, obtained in previous step, onto the ground-truth sketch S (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The second step of the generative refinement pipeline. Copy the quadtree of \hat{S} into S .

We will thus model the distribution $p(S|S', c)$ as $p(S|\hat{S}, c)$, or equivalently, in terms of the leaves of the quadtree:

$$p(S|\hat{S}, c) = p(\{l_s\}|\{\hat{l}_s\}, c)$$

which, by the property of joint probability, we can equivalently write as:

$$\begin{aligned}
p(\{I_s\}|\{\hat{I}_{\hat{S}}\}, c) &= p\left(I_s^{(1)}, \dots, I_s^{(L)} | \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(1)}, \dots, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(L)}, c\right) \\
&= p\left(I_s^{(1)} | \{\hat{I}_{\hat{S}}\}, c\right) \cdot p\left(I_s^{(2)} | I_s^{(1)}, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(2)}, \dots, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(L)}, c\right) \dots \\
&\dots \\
&\cdot p\left(I_s^{(i)} | I_s^{(1)}, \dots, I_s^{(i-1)}, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(i)}, \dots, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(L)}, c\right) \\
&\dots \\
&\cdot p\left(I_s^{(L)} | I_s^{(1)}, \dots, I_s^{(L-1)}, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(L)}, c\right) \\
&= \prod_{i=1}^L p\left(I_s^{(i)} | I_s^{(1)}, \dots, I_s^{(i-1)}, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(i)}, \dots, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(L)}, c\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where L is the number of leaves.

Each individual distribution is conditioned on the leaves of \hat{S} but also on all the previously generated leaves of S , which will replace the corresponding ones in \hat{S} . This will enable a *coherent and aware generation* of what has been previously generated.

Note that the formulation (1) is quite naive and not scalable, as the generation of a single leaf *needs all the initial and previously generated leaves*. For a better scalability, to generate a particular leaf we will use a much lighter condition that we will indicate as the *context of the leaf to generate*.

To this end, we define the **context of a leaf** $\hat{I}_{\hat{S}(i)}$ as the set of spatial neighbors of the leaf itself and all of its ancestors. Specifically, given the leaf $\hat{I}_{\hat{S}(i)}$, its spatial neighbors will correspond to the 3x3 grid of tiles where the leaf itself is at the center of the grid, and each tile has the same size as the leaf. The subsequent neighbors will be those of the 3x3 grid where the parent of the leaf is at the center, and each tile has the size of the parent. This process continues until the root itself is reached (the top-down view of \hat{S}). The entire process is illustrated in Figure 5. This context satisfies three fundamental properties:

- The context of a leaf $\hat{I}_{\hat{S}(i)}$ must contain a lossless information about the surrounding pixels. This will help generate a leaf that is consistent with the values of the surrounding pixels.
- The context of a leaf $\hat{I}_{\hat{S}(i)}$ must contain progressively coarser information as it moves away from the target leaf.
- The context of a leaf must provide an overview of the current version of \hat{S} .

Therefore, let \bar{S}_i denote the data at step i of the refinement, i.e.:

$$\bar{S}_i = \{I_s^{(1)}, \dots, I_s^{(i-1)}, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(i)}, \dots, \hat{I}_{\hat{S}}^{(L)}\}$$

and defining $\aleph(\bar{I}_{\bar{S}(i)})$ as the context of a leaf in \bar{S} , the formulation (1) becomes:

$$p(\{I_s\}|\{\hat{I}_{\hat{S}}\}, c) = \prod_{i=1}^L p\left(I_s^{(i)} | \aleph(\bar{I}_{\bar{S}(i)}), c\right) \tag{2}$$

During training, we will predict the generative refinement of the leaf $I_s^{(i)}$ using the class c and the context $\aleph(\cdot)$ of the leaf, as shown in Figure 6.

3.2. Generative refinement with autoregressive modeling

To model each individual distribution in (2), we use a Transformer architecture (Vaswani, Shazeer, Parmar, Uszkoreit, Jones, Gomez, Kaiser and Polosukhin (2017)). Before training the Transformer \mathcal{T}_θ , we train a Vector Quantized Variational Autoencoder (VQ-VAE) (Van Den Oord, Vinyals et al. (2017)) to learn a discrete representation of the tiles at various resolutions they may have during the context creation process (Figure 5). This model acts as a **tokenizer**: each tile of size $W' \times H'$ is encoded into a sequence of discrete indices belonging to a codebook. Once trained, the VQ-VAE is used to tokenize the refined patch into a sequence of discrete tokens, which are then used for training the Transformer.

Figure 5: Process of creating the context of a leaf. Starting from the target leaf, the 3×3 tiles around it are taken with the leaf in the center. The same is done with the parent of the leaf until we reach the root itself. Each tile, regardless of the level, has the same resolution.

Figure 6: To refine a leaf and make the approach more scalable, we consider its spatial context by including node's adjacent neighborhood (i.e., centered 3×3 grid) for each level up to the root. The nearby nodes in blue, which extend beyond the image, are referred to as *dummy nodes* and have a fixed value.

The encoder is a vision encoder (Dosovitskiy, Beyer, Kolesnikov, Weissenborn, Zhai, Unterthiner, Dehghani, Minderer, Heigold, Gelly et al. (2020)) that extracts features from \bar{S}_i to enable the cross-attention mechanism with the decoder. However, unlike the classic ViT, we do not use all patches of \bar{S}_i , as this would make the method unscalable. Instead, we select the context $\aleph(\hat{I}_{s(i)})$ of the leaf to be refined. A notable property of our methodology is that *the sequence produced by context extraction is always of the same length*, regardless of the level at which the leaf is located. Indeed, if the octree has a maximum depth of D , then the context $\aleph(\hat{I}_{s(i)})$ is a fixed sequence of length $D \times 9 + 1$, where 9 represents the neighbors at each level, and the addition of 1 accounts for the contribution of the root. However, if a leaf belongs to an intermediate level $0 < i < D$, its context still has the same length, but starting from a higher level, we use fixed and neutral values for the first elements of the sequence.

The Transformer's decoder outputs a sequence of probability distributions over the codebook indices, thus modeling the distribution of the refined leaf given the visual features extracted by the encoder. A visual representation of the architecture is shown in Figure 8.

We train a VQ-VAE to compress each individual tile into a set of integer values \mathbf{z} . To avoid low perplexity, and thus inefficient use of the codebook, we train the VQ-VAE not on the sparse data, but on a different representation that "intelligently fills" the empty spaces, preventing codebook collapse, which would introduce a strong bias in the transformer, leading to the prediction of repetitive sequences or overemphasizing certain tokens. This representation consists of calculating the **Signed Distance Fields (SDF)** of the sparse data. A SDF is a scalar field that represents

the distance from a given point to the nearest surface. In our case, the surface corresponds to the stroke of the sketch. Positive values indicate points outside the stroke, while negative values indicate points inside it. This allows us to create a continuous representation of the shapes present in the sparse data, effectively filling in gaps and providing a more informative input for the VQ-VAE.

Figure 7: Handling the Signed Distance Field (SDF) representation of sparse data helps VQ-VAE to have high perplexity (high codebook utilization) and thus avoid strong biases by the transformer in predicting certain classes.

Specifically, the convolutional encoder performs a downsampling of each tile l to a smaller continuous spatial resolution:

$$\mathcal{V}_{\text{Encoder}}(l) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_K\}, \quad \text{where } v_j \in \mathbb{R}^{K \cdot D}$$

Subsequently, each continuous encoding v_i will be mapped to the nearest element of the codebook of vectors $\mathbb{P} = \{p_i\}_{i=1}^Q \in \mathbb{R}^{Q \cdot D}$, where Q is the total number of vectors in the codebook and D is the dimension of each vector. Therefore, in the end, each tile will be associated with a unique set of vectors:

$$\mathbf{z} = \{q_1, q_2, \dots, q_K\}, \quad \text{where } q_i = \min_{p_j \in \mathbb{P}} \|v_i - p_j\|$$

whose codebook indices are chosen by the so-called quantizer $\mathcal{V}_{\text{Quantizer}}(\mathbf{z})$. Each tile is then decompressed using a convolutional decoder:

$$\mathcal{V}_{\text{Decoder}}(\mathbf{z}) = \hat{l}$$

The entire model is trained end-to-end by minimizing the following loss (Corona-Figueroa, Bond-Taylor, Bhowmik, Gaus, Breckon, Shum and Willcocks (2023)):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{VQ} = & \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}(\hat{l}, l) + \mathcal{L}_{\text{codebook}}(v, \mathbf{z}) \\ & + w_g \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{generator}}(\hat{l}) + w_d \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{discriminator}}(\hat{l}, l) \\ & + w_p \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{perceptual}}(\hat{l}, l) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The entire pipeline (generation + generative refinement) is shown in Figure 8, while the pseudocode for training and inference is shown in algorithms (1) and (2).

4. Experimental Validation

To validate our methodology, we tested **ViSketch-GPT** on two types of tasks: sketch generation and classification.

4.1. Dataset

The proposed methodology is evaluated on the QuickDraw dataset (Ha and Eck (2018)), which is a collection of sketches created for the Google application *Quick, Draw!*, an online game in which users were asked to quickly draw, in less than 20 seconds, sketches related to specific categories. The dataset consists of 50 million sketches across 345 categories. Each sketch in QuickDraw is represented as a sequence of *pen stroke actions*, defined by five elements:

$$(\Delta_x, \Delta_y, p_1, p_2, p_3)$$

where:

Algorithm 1: Stage2: training**1 repeat**2 Choose random triplet ($S_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H}, S'_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{W' \times H'}, c \in \mathbb{Z}^+$)3 Resize S'_0 to high resolution $\rightarrow \hat{S}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H}$ 4 Compute the leaves of \hat{S}_0 via quadtree $\rightarrow \{\hat{l}_{s_i}\}_{i=1}^L$ 5 $l \sim \text{Uniform}(1 \dots L)$ 6 Replace the leaves preceding l with the corresponding tiles of S_0

$$\{\hat{l}_{\hat{s}_i} | \hat{l}_{\hat{s}_i} = l_{s_i} \text{ for } i = 1 \dots (l-1)\}$$

7 Compute target leaf context $\rightarrow \mathfrak{N}(\hat{l}_{s(i)})$

8 Tokenize the refined leaf using the learned codebook

$$t = \mathcal{V}_{\text{Quantizer}}(\mathcal{V}_{\text{Encoder}}(l_{s_i}))$$

9 Compute the logits using Vision Encoder Decoder

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathcal{T}_\theta(\mathfrak{N}(\hat{l}_{s(i)}), t, c)$$

where \mathbf{g} is a sequence of K logits of length Q . Each logit is a vector as long as the VQ-VAE codebook, containing information on which codebook index is most plausible to sample.

10 Apply softmax for each one of the K logits:

$$\hat{y}_{k,j} = \frac{e^{g_{k,j}}}{\sum_{q'=1}^Q e^{g_{k,q'}}}, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, Q$$

11 Compute the loss function (cross-entropy)

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{q=1}^Q y_{k,q} \log \hat{y}_{k,q}$$

12 Take gradient descent step on

$$\nabla_\theta \mathcal{L}$$

13 **until** convergence

Figure 8: Architectural overview of the pure generation and generative refinement process. Given a class c , a low-resolution version of the SDF is generated, which is then scaled by a trivial resize to the desired resolution. The generative refinement stage, repeated for each leaf of the quadtree, restores the missing details. We end by clipping the SDF to get the data back in its sparse representation.

- Δ_x, Δ_y represent the offset from the previous point.
- p_1 is a binary value indicating whether the pen is touching the paper (1) or lifted (0), thereby determining whether a line is drawn to the current point.
- p_2 is a binary indicator specifying whether the pen is lifted after reaching the current point (1) or not (0).

Algorithm 2: Stage2: inference

-
- 1 **Input:** $S'_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{W' \times H'}$, $c \in \mathbb{Z}^+$
 - 2 Resize S'_0 to high resolution $\rightarrow \hat{S}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{W \times H}$
 - 3 Compute the leaves of S_0 via quadtree $\rightarrow \{\hat{l}_{s_i}\}_{i=1}^L$
 - 4 **for** \hat{l}_{s_i} **in** $\{\hat{l}_{s_i}\}_{i=1}^L$ **do**:
 - 5 Initialize token sequence $t = []$
 - 6 **for** $d = 1$ to K **do**:
 - 7 Compute the context of the leaf $\mathfrak{N}(\hat{l}_{s_i})$
 - 8 Compute logits using Vision Encoder Decoder:

$$\mathbf{g} = \mathcal{T}_\theta(\mathfrak{N}(\hat{l}_{s_i}), t, c)$$

- 9 Apply softmax to obtain probabilities:

$$\hat{y}_j = \frac{e^{g_j}}{\sum_{q'=1}^Q e^{g_{q'}}}, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, Q$$

- 10 Sample token from predicted distribution:

$$t_d \sim \text{Categorical}(\hat{\mathbf{y}})$$

- 11 Append sampled token t_d to sequence t
- 12 **end for**
- 13 Decode token sequence into leaf patch:

$$I_{s_d} = \mathcal{V}_{\text{Decoder}}(t)$$

- 14 Update quadtree
 - 15 **end for**
-

- p_3 denotes whether the drawing sequence ends at the current point (1) or continues (0).

In order to use our methodology, we transform each sketch into an image, which we then convert it into an SDF.

We followed the pre-processing method and training split suggested by Ha and Eck (2018), where each class has 70K training samples, 2.5K validation, and 2.5K test samples in the QuickDraw dataset. In order to align with various competitors, we also simplified the sketches by applying the *Ramer-Douglas-Peucker* (RDP) algorithm to handle sequences with a maximum length of 321.

4.2. Results on Sketch Generation Task

For the sketch generation task, we followed the methodology proposed by SketchGPT (Tiwari et al. (2024)) to ensure a fair comparison with SketchRNN. Their approach quantifies the generative capability of a model by evaluating how well a classifier can distinguish generated sketches.

To maintain a fair comparison, we selected the same seven classes from the QuickDraw dataset (bus, cat, elephant, flamingo, owl, pig and sheep) and trained a ResNet34 model to classify sketches from these categories. The model was trained until it reached a validation accuracy of 87.92%. Subsequently, we generated 1,000 sketches per class, resulting in a total of 7,000 sketches, which were then fed into the previously trained ResNet34 to measure top-1 and top-3 accuracy.

Table 1 presents the performance results of the models. Additionally, we report the results of our model both with and without the refinement stage. Our findings highlight the critical role of the use of SDF in the first stage and the use of this refinement stage in significantly improving generation quality, leading to a **substantial increase in classification accuracy compared to the state-of-the-art**. This improvement is likely due to the refinement process adding missing or unclear details, enabling the CNN to classify the generated sketches with higher confidence. Figure 9 presents some examples of generated sketches for the target classes.

Method	Top-1 Acc.	Top-3 Acc.
SketchRNN	44.6%	79.1%
SketchGPT	50.4%	81.7%
ViSketch-GPT (our) (w/o Ref.)	51.6%	83.2%
ViSketch-GPT (our) (w Ref.)	63.4%	88.8%

Table 1

Performance comparison of different sketch generation models. The designations "w/o" and "w" indicate results without and with the refinement stage, respectively.

4.3. Results on Sketch Classification Task

The Sketch Classification task is a typical task in which, given a sketch, one aims to classify it correctly into its corresponding category. We used 100 categories with 5K training samples, 2.5K validation samples, and 2.5K test samples from the QuickDraw dataset. We considered, as done previously by several competitors (Tiwari et al. (2024); Lin et al. (2020)), evaluating whether the methodology could also be used as a feature extractor to train a classifier on top. In our case, given a sketch, we want to assess whether the features extracted via the proposed algorithm are significant enough to train a classifier that is more accurate than one trained using features extracted by other methods.

Competitors

We conduct a comparative analysis of multiple baseline models:

1. **HOG-SVM** (Eitz, Hildebrand, Boubekeur and Alexa (2010)): A conventional approach that employs Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) features combined with a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier to perform classification tasks.
2. **Ensemble** (Li, Song, Gong et al. (2013)): This model integrates various types of sketch features and is evaluated on classification tasks.
3. **BiLSTM** (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997)): A three-layer bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) model is utilized to assess recognition and retrieval tasks on sequential sketch data. The hidden state dimensionality is set to 512.
4. **Sketch-a-Net** (Yu et al. (2015)): A convolutional neural network specifically designed for sketch data.
5. **DSSA** (Song, Yu, Song, Xiang and Hospedales (2017)): This approach extends Sketch-a-Net by incorporating an attention module and a high-order energy triplet loss function.
6. **ResNet** (He, Zhang, Ren and Sun (2016)): A widely used residual neural network architecture in computer vision, primarily designed for image recognition tasks.
7. **TC-Net** (Lin, Fu, Lu, Gong, Xue and Jiang (2019)): A network based on DenseNet ?, applied to sketch-based image retrieval tasks. We utilize a pre-trained version for classification and retrieval experiments.
8. **SketchRNN** (Ha and Eck (2018)): A variational autoencoder that employs an LSTM-based encoder-decoder architecture for sketch generation. In our experiments, we adapt this model to evaluate the sketch gestalt task.
9. **SketchBert** (Lin et al. (2020)): A BERT-based model, adapted for free-hand sketches, uses BERT's ability to capture contextual relationships in sequences to interpret sketches as temporal pen strokes.
10. **SketchGPT** (Tiwari et al. (2024)): A model that employs a sequence-to-sequence autoregressive approach for sketch generation and completion, mapping complex sketches into simplified sequences of abstract primitives. By leveraging the next-token prediction strategy, it learns sketch patterns, enabling accurate drawing creation, completion, and categorization.

The training and validation subsets are used for model training, while evaluations are conducted on the test set.

Implementation Details

The methodology was originally designed to refine a leaf \hat{l}_{s_i} given its context $\mathfrak{N}(\hat{l}_{s_i})$. However, to classify the entire sketch, we would need to process, after calculating the quadtree, L leaves of the sketch to obtain its class prediction. Therefore, we can interpret the classification task as an *ensemble voting*, where each leaf, via its context $\mathfrak{N}(\cdot)$, provides its "proposal" for the class vote. We will therefore add a CLS token, which we will use after processing it with

ViSketch-GPT

Figure 9: Some results of the generation task. Given a class, a low-resolution version of the SDF of the sketch is generated, which is then refined in a generative way and then clipped to obtain the final sketch.

the encoder together with the leaf's context. Finally, we will use the L extracted CLS tokens, process them with a simple self-attention layer, and extract the final CLS token to make the prediction with a simple linear layer. Since pre-training tasks on unlabeled data in NLP have shown great potential in improving the performance of models on downstream tasks, following a similar approach to SketchBert with its "Sketch Gestalt" task (Lin et al. (2020)), we pre-trained the VisionEncoderDecoder on the *completion* task. Specifically, given a sketch, we calculate its quadtree, choose a random leaf, and mask it. Then, we train the model to predict the VQ-VAE codebook IDs, which, when decoded, represent the missing 2D tile. This task helps meaningfully initialize the encoder weights, which we then

Figure 10: Architectural overview for the classification task. Once the encoder is pre-trained, it is used to extract context features for each leaf. Then the CLS is used as the vote of each leaf which is processed with the others for class prediction.

Methods	Top-1 Acc.	Top-5 Acc.
HOG-SVM	56.13	78.34
Ensemble	66.98	89.32
Bi-LSTM	86.14	97.03
Sketch-a-Net	75.33	90.21
DSSA	79.47	92.41
ResNet18	83.97	95.98
ResNet50	86.03	97.06
TCNet	86.79	97.08
Sketch-BERT (100 × 5K)	85.82	97.31
Sketch-BERT (200 × 5K)	84.89	97.14
Sketch-BERT (345 × 5K)	85.73	97.31
Sketch-BERT (345 × 70K)	88.30	97.82
Sketch-GPT (50 × 5K)	83.58	93.65
ViSketch-GPT (our)	94.45	99.72

Table 2

Comparison with state-of-the-art methods on sketch classification on the QuickDraw dataset. The notation (C × N) indicates the amount of pretraining done (i.e., with C classes and N samples for each class) before fine-tuning on the classes to be evaluated.

use to extract the leaf features for the classification task discussed earlier.

Our architecture for pre-training has a depth of 6 in both the encoder and decoder, a hidden size of 256, and a number of heads equal to 8. For the pre-training phase, we use the same classes and sample size as SketchBert, i.e., 100 classes and 5K training examples, 2.5K for validation and testing, with an image resolution of 128 (leaf size of 32). An architectural overview is shown in Figure 10.

Discussion

Table 2 shows the top-1 and top-3 accuracy results on the QuickDraw dataset for both the competitors and our model. The results demonstrate that **our model significantly outperforms the state-of-the-art (SOTA)**, setting new performance benchmarks. Moreover, it is important to note that our pre-training was done on only 100 classes and 5K samples. Despite this minimal pre-training, our model outperformed others, including SketchBert, which was trained on up to 345 classes and 70K samples. This performance gain is likely attributed to the voting mechanism, which allows each leaf to contribute to the classification, helps capture those subtle details that ultimately make the difference in classifying the sketch rather than relying on a holistic approach.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we tackled the challenge of generating and classifying human sketches, a complex task due to the high variability in strokes and representations. To overcome this difficulty, we introduced a novel algorithm capable of extracting significant multi-scale features, leveraging their collaboration to improve both sketch classification and generation. Our experiments demonstrate that this strategy achieves an unprecedented level of classification accuracy and generation quality, highlighting the effectiveness of our approach in capturing intricate details. These details enhance the classifier’s confidence in understanding sketches and make the generator more aware of the characteristics that distinguish different sketches.

While the results are encouraging, the proposed method has some limitations. In particular, our framework can be extended to higher-resolution sketches, and while this does not introduce memory issues, it remains an autoregressive approach that requires considerable time. A promising future direction is the exploration of parallelization techniques for leaf generation to accelerate the process and improve scalability.

Ultimately, our work represents a step forward in understanding and modeling human sketches, opening new perspectives for applications in areas such as visual recognition and AI-assisted creativity.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT, an AI language model developed by OpenAI, in order to correct grammatical errors. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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